

NATIONAL SECURITY, CONFRONTATION AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALISATION

Adizov Azim Tolibovich

Independent researcher at Bukhara State University

Abstract. This article analyzes the essence of the globalization process, its impact on national security, interethnic relations and social stability. It also covers the confrontational processes arising as a result of globalization, interethnic conflicts and the issues of preventing threats arising from them. The study reveals the positive and negative aspects of globalization, the importance of protecting national interests and developing democratic values.

Keywords: globalization, confrontation, conflict, interethnic relations, threat, national security, integration, national interest, stability.

Introduction The 21st century is a new stage in human development, in which globalization processes directly affect the lives of all countries and peoples of the world. As a result of the development of modern information and communication technologies, economic integration and international cooperation, the interconnection between countries is increasing. At the same time, the globalization process, along with new opportunities, also creates various threats and conflicts. In particular, the issues of protecting national interests, preserving national values and ensuring security are gaining urgent importance.

The essence and modern interpretations of globalization Globalization is characterized by the acceleration and deepening of economic, political, cultural and information relations between countries and peoples. As a result of this process, the world is increasingly becoming a single space. However, the results of globalization are not the same for all countries. Researchers point to the development of international cooperation, the expansion of the exchange of science and technology, the improvement of the investment climate and the strengthening of international law as positive aspects of globalization. At the same time, the increase in economic inequality, the weakening of some cultures under the influence of mass culture, the erosion of national values, and the intensification of transnational threats are manifested as its negative consequences.

As Farida Yuldasheva noted, protection from the negative consequences of globalization and its effective use in the interests of national interests have become an important task of every state. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a deep scientific analysis of globalization processes and form a development model based on democratic values. The social essence of confrontation and conflicts Confrontation or conflict is an integral part of the development of society. Conflict is derived from the Latin word "conflictus" and means a clash of interests, views, and goals. Since there are different social groups, strata, and nationalities in any society, it is natural for conflicts of interest to arise between them. The main causes of conflicts can be economic interests, the struggle for political power, religious and cultural differences, territorial claims, and historical factors.

Especially in the context of globalization, the acceleration of information flows is causing some conflicts to become more acute. In this regard, the existence of mechanisms for managing conflicts and resolving them peacefully is of great importance in any society. Democratic institutions, civil society and the rule of law are important factors that prevent conflicts from taking a destructive turn.

Interethnic relations and factors of origin of conflicts. Interethnic relations are an important component of state stability. Interethnic conflicts often arise under the influence of factors related to territorial claims, political interests, economic inequality, religious differences and historical memory. Studies show that the aggravation of interethnic conflicts is caused by such factors as the degradation of national values, the restriction of the rights of certain nationalities and social injustice. This is confirmed by the conflicts in the former Yugoslavia, ethnic conflicts in the Caucasus region and many other examples. To strengthen interethnic harmony in multinational societies, it is necessary to

develop democratic and legal mechanisms that equally protect the rights and interests of all nations. In this regard, Uzbekistan's policy of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance is an important experience.

Issues of national security in the context of globalization In the process of globalization, the concept of security has gone beyond the scope of traditional military security and has also included areas such as economic, environmental, information and ideological security. Today, the problems of international terrorism, extremism, drug trafficking, transnational crime and cybersecurity are manifested as global threats. Modern information technologies allow these threats to freely cross geographical borders. To ensure national security, states need to develop international cooperation, improve the legal framework and strengthen the ideological immunity of citizens. In particular, protecting young people from the influence of foreign ideas and harmonizing national and universal values are among the urgent tasks of today. Preventing threats and protecting national interests Threats can be directed at various spheres of state and social life. They are of a natural and social nature and pose a risk of harming national interests.

The main ways to protect national interests are:

- improving the political and legal culture of citizens;
- preservation and development of national values;
- compliance with international law;
- strengthening interethnic harmony and religious tolerance;
- effectively combating terrorism and extremism; increasing economic independence and competitiveness.

One of the important factors of national security is the social activity and high spirituality of citizens. The loyalty and responsibility of members of society to their state are important in preventing threats. Conclusion Globalization is an inevitable process of modern world development. While it opens up new opportunities for humanity, it also creates various dangers and threats. In particular, the issues of national security, interethnic relations and the preservation of spiritual values are gaining particular relevance in the context of globalization. Therefore, each state should effectively use the positive aspects of globalization and minimize its negative consequences through scientifically based policies, democratic institutions and the development of civil society. Only then will it be possible to protect national interests, ensure sustainable development and security.

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